

REUSE OF EXISTING STEEL PILES THROUGH INTEGRITY ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

This paper refers to the reuse of steel piles of existing marine facilities, in the frame of the modernization of the oldest refinery in the Arabian Gulf area. The first units were built in the 1930s and two wharves for exporting oil products were added respectively in 1940 and 1960.

The refurbishment of existing structures was selected, rather than going for the provision of brand-new facilities.

Very few and uncontrolled data were available for the driven steel piles supporting these wharves, hence the main challenge was assessing the existing piles' integrity underwater and their penetration into seabed, while keeping these wharves operational.

The option to carry out a static load test on an existing pile appeared immediately to be dangerous, specifically the possible pile destruction, damages to surrounding piles, and disruption to wharf operations.

A Sonic Integrity Testing (or eco-test, or PIT) campaign was instead proposed on a representative number of piles. This test is a widely-used NDE method to assess piles' conditions.

Results allowed for determining all data for the structural verification of piles for their reuse.

The sustainable option to revamp existing structures may benefit from this simple and inexpensive NDE method.

Keywords: revamping, marine works, existing piles, reuse.

INTRODUCTION

The Bapco Modernization Program is an engineering, procurement and construction project awarded in 2018 to the Joint Venture of Technip Energies (Italy), Tecnicas Reunidas (Spain) and Samsung (Korea) for the expansion and modernization of the oldest refinery in the Arabian Gulf, where the first units were built in the 1930s, located at Sitra, Bahrain. The attention to environment in the Kingdom of Bahrain has posed a number of challenges throughout the project execution – particularly for the marine works – under the responsibility of Technip Energies Italy.

BAPCO WHARF HISTORICAL OVERVIEW

The marine facilities of the existing refinery include two wharves (2+4 Berths) for exporting the products via seagoing vessels.

The “T-Head Wharf” was built in the 1940s and allows the simultaneous loading of four tankers, while the “Island Wharf” was built in the 1960s for the concurrent loading of two tankers.

The modernization of these berths mainly consists of the installation of n.17 new marine loading arms, manufactured by *Kanon* (Holland), to replace the existing loading system by flexible hoses.

Therefore, Technip Energies Italy had to assess the integrity of existing structures as its first task to confirm their suitability for the loads imposed by the BMP Project and consequently to design the refurbishment works required.

Furthermore, the design had to carefully take into account the need to keep these wharves in operation, with severe restrictions on the possibility to execute “hot works” during the loading of certain highly flammable products.

Fig 1 Project location

PROJECT OVERVIEW AND DESIGN SCOPE

Design purpose and scope

The purpose of the design was to check the adequacy of the T-Head wharf and Island structure in view of the current design codes and the main following aspects:

- Analysis of environmental loads acting on T-Head and Island Wharves combined with relevant water levels updated to nowadays data;
- Evaluation of the final load configuration after the implementation of BAPCO Modernization Program, here called “Post-BMP” condition.

Fig 2 Satellite view of the wharves area

Layer 3 (CAL): Very weak to weak, medium to highly weathered CALCISILTITE, CALCARENITE, CALCILUTITE, dark grey to grey, thickness of 21.0 to 26.0 m. The layer has multiple pockets of fully weathered calcilutite. Most boreholes end within this layer.

Layer 4 (LIM): Very weak to moderately strong, moderately weathered LIMESTONE, of white to light yellow, up to the maximum survey depth of 40 m below seabed.

The encountered stratigraphy indicates that a competent layer of highly weathered very weak to weak rock layer (CAL) starts at approximately 6.0 to 10.0 m below seabed, while a medium weathered very weak to weak rock layer (LIM) has been identified in only few boreholes and starts at approximately 24.0 to 30.0 m depth below seabed.

Table 1. Geotechnical design parameters and design soil profile of the Island wharf

Layer	σ_1 (kPa)	σ_3 (kPa)	GSI	m	D	γ (kN/m ³)	c (kPa)	φ (deg)	Em (MPa)
CSS	-	-	-	-	-	17.0	-	30	5
SIL	-	-	-	-	-	17.0	240 ¹⁾	-	50
CAL	70	30	45	12	0	19.0	13	48	90

Layer	Thickness (m)	N _{SPT} avg	RQD			UCS (MPa)			E _i (MPa)	PL avg (MPa)
			min	max	avg	min	max	Avg Shaft / End	avg	
CSS	1.0 - 7.5	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SIL	0 - 2.5	48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CAL	≥22.5	-	0	94	40	0.1	4.90	1.0/0.7	250	N/A

Table 2. Geotechnical design parameters and design soil profile of the T-head wharf

Layer	σ_1 (kPa)	σ_3 (kPa)	GSI	m	D	γ (kN/m ³)	c (kPa)	φ (deg)	Em (MPa)
CSS	-	-	-	-	-	17.0	-	30	5
SIL	-	-	-	-	-	17.0	200 ¹⁾	-	40
CAL	70	30	45	12	0	19.0	13	48	90
LIM	340	140	45	12	0	20.0	45	43	480

Layer	Thickness (m)	N _{SPT} avg	RQD			UCS (Mpa)			E _i (Mpa)	PL avg (Mpa)
			min	max	avg	min	max	Avg Shaft / End	avg	
CSS	2.5 - 4.0	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SIL	3.0 - 5.5	40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CAL	24.5 - 25.50	-	0	94	40	0.35	6.77	1.0/0.7	200	0.26 ¹⁾
LIM	≥8.5	-	13	72	33	3.49	3.49	3.5	N/A	1.00 ²⁾

Geotechnical parameters evaluation methods

The engineering properties of soils have been evaluated on the basis of borehole logs, layers descriptions, grain size distribution, SPT N-values and the available laboratory tests experienced with similar layers in the broader area. The rock mass equivalent Mohr-Coulomb strength properties (ϕ , c) and E-moduli have been evaluated on the basis of the Hoek-Brown model. The required model parameters (GSI, m_i, D) have been estimated based on the rock type, Solid Core Recovery (SCR), Rock Quality Designation (RQD), Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) tests and Point Load Index (PL) tests.

Structural Design Method

The structural analysis for in-place conditions was conducted (by COWI) as a classical static linear analysis of a 3D space frame computer model of the main structure based on the stiffness method. Structural analyses are carried out by using Autodesk Robot Structural Analysis Professional 2019.1 performing linear static analysis based on the displacement and stiffness method.

The computer model reflected the correct global stiffness of the structure and included the substructure (i.e., piles, capping beams, stringers, horizontal/vertical bracings) and superstructure (e.g., upper platform) including pipe and equipment supports. Piles were modeled down to 12 m below seabed level, with lateral and vertical springs to simulate the soil stiffness derived from the geotechnical data.

To this aim it was therefore essential to assess the structural integrity of existing piles.

Fig 4 Post BMP Structural model general view (blue = underwater bracings grid added) and Typical detail of soil springs modelling (right)

EXISTING PILES AVAILABLE INFORMATION AND SUSTAINABLE DESIGN APPROACH

As already highlighted in the above chapter, the project required collection of a large amount of information from different disciplines: geotechnical, bathymetry and seabed mapping survey, and site met-ocean characterization.

The T-Head Wharf is supported on about 1000 driven “H-300” piles, while the Island Wharf is founded on 50 driven tubular piles, 16” and 24” diameter. The information available about these existing structures at the beginning of the project was basically the following:

1. Original hand-made drawings and piling plans, with no certainty that they were reflecting the actual as-built status of these old structures.
2. Divers’ survey report of the piles, carried out in 2017 including: visual inspection, Ultrasonic Test (UT) thickness readings, and Cathodic protection (CP) potential readings on a percentage of piles.

This information was of course neither sufficient to assess the actual penetration in the seabed nor the structural integrity of these piles. Therefore, it would not have been possible to carry out a reliable design verification of the existing structures subjected to the new loads of the project. The idea of going for brand new structures on new piles was initially reviewed and discarded in view of the space constraints, of the

environmental impact and of the need to interconnect anyway the new and old structures. The UT and CP readings of the survey were indicating respectively that piles' thickness has decreased of a negligible amount over the 60+ years and that the existing impressed current CP system was still effective. These considerations lead to the sustainable decision to reuse the existing piles. The option to carry out a static load test on one of the existing piles was examined and abandoned considering the inherent risk of permanent damage to the tested pile and to the nearby ones being used as reaction piles, as well as the disruption to the ongoing loading operations caused before, during and after the test in case of pile failure.

Fig 5 T-Head Wharf existing structures as built documentation

Therefore, a PIT testing campaign was conceived and proposed to the client on a representative sample of piles, about 10% (red dots in Fig. 7 and 8), selected on the basis of the highest loads anticipated from the preliminary structural design, and on the diving inspection reports (black dots Fig. 7 and 8):

Fig 7 T-Head Wharf plan of inspected piles and PIT tests

Fig 8 T-Island Wharf plan of inspected piles and PIT tests

PIT METHOD PROJECT APPLICATION

On October 30 and 31, and November 1–4, 2019, tests on n. 113 piles by “Pile Integrity Test” (PIT) were performed as follows:

T Head North: 37 H piles, having dimensions 310x290x10. The tests were performed 70 cm below the joint H Beam piles, the sensor was fixed on an H pile by an aluminum base clamped by a bolt. This arrangement was requested because the top of the piles was not accessible for a correct connection of the geophone and a proper impact. The hammer blows were applied along the side of the piles in a sub-vertical direction. This arrangement usually introduces a high frequency component due to the contribution of the first 70 cm of pile above the sensor. It's possible to partially reduce this noise with proper analog filters.

T Head South: 41 H piles, having dimensions 310x290x10. As per T Head North piles, the tests were performed 70 cm below the joint H Beam piles, the sensor was fixed on an H pile by an aluminum base clamped by bolt.

Island: 35 piles, having diameters 16” and 24”. The tests were performed directly at the top of each pile.

Fig 9 T- Mechanical coupling setup on steel pile

For the PIT tests, the Most/EAM10 equipment was used as detailed in Fig. 10.

Equipment, procedures and reports are in agreement with the specifications of the French Standard *AFNOR NF P 94-160-2* and the American Standard *ASTM – D5882-00* “Standard Test Method for Low Strain Integrity Testing of Piles”.

Hammer with interchangeable tips, weight from 1.5 to 3.5 kg
Geophone Sensor SM4A (or Accelerometer PCB 353B34):

- sensitivity: 100 mV/g
- Frequency range: 0.7 ÷ 7000 Hz

Notebook Panasonic CF18-CF19-CF71

Acquisition A/D converter National Instruments NI DAQ Card 6062E

- channels: 16
- max frequency speed: 500 kHz
- gain: x 0.5 ÷ x 1000 in 10 steps
- resolution: 12 bit

Acquisition-processing software National Instruments
LabView/MOST-EAM10

Fig 10 T- Most/EAM10 equipment used, component detail

The PIT signals contain the following parameters:

- The number of tested piles;
- The reflection time (ms = milliseconds);
- The lengths L1 – L2 of steel-piles calculated by two velocities of propagation: 5000 - 5200 m/s;
- The Time (S1 and S2) of secondary reflections, the first caused from the presence of soil (CSS and SIL) at the bottom of the sea (S1). The second (S2) is the elevation of the bed rock (CAL).

The scales of the attached PIT signals are:

- Horizontal scale = time base: 2 ms (milliseconds) / division
- Vertical scale = amplitude of signals: changeable by exponential amplifier

Note: all signals have been elaborated with the same vertical amplification.

PIT METHOD RESULTS PRESENTATION

An example of PIT tests results are shown into the Tables 3 and Figure 11.

Table 3. T- Head – North – PIT Tests Results on H Piles

Pile N°	Time T ^a (ms)	Depth L1 ^{a1} (m)	Depth L2 ^{a2} (m)	Time T1 ^b (ms)	Avg Depth CSS/SIL ^{b1} (m)	Time T2 ^c (ms)	Avg Depth CAL ^{c1} (m)
05 D	12.1	30.3	31.5	5.7	14.5	8.7	22.2
07 D	11.2	27.9	29.0	6.1	15.6	8.6	21.9
07 C	11.3	28.3	29.5	6.1	15.6	8.6	21.9
07 B	11.5	28.8	30.0	5.7	14.5	8.6	21.9

LEGEND	T ^a Pile reflection time (no defects)	L1 ^{a1} Length of pile (V = 5000 m/sec)	L2 ^{a2} Length of pile (V = 5200 m/sec)
	T1 ^b Soil (CSS/SIL) reflection time	CSS/SIL ^{b1} Soil average depth (V _{avg} = 5100 m/sec)	
	T2 ^c Bed rock (CAL) reflection time	CAL ^{c1} Bed rock average depth (V _{avg} = 5100 m/sec)	

In Table 3 the Time (S1 and S2) of secondary reflections, the first caused from the presence of soil (CSS and SIL) at the bottom of the sea (S1). The second (S2) is the elevation of the bed rock (CAL).

Fig 11 T- Island steel piles – Bed Rock – 3D View

The PIT tests allowed for the conclusion of the following:

- All tested piles are upright for the lengths L1-L2 show on the attached tables of PIT results and signals. The shown lengths of the tested piles aren't affected by important defects (cracks, folds, section restrictions, etc.).
- The dynamic of all acquired signals at T Head is influenced by the free shaft in the water. The noise that afflicts PIT signal on H-beam elements is due to the geometric configuration (splice) of the piles and the arrangement of the transducer (lateral to the H-beam) and it is difficult to filter. Despite this, the signals are intelligible to show the length of the piles and the depth of the soil (CSS/SIL) and bed rock (CAL).
- The acquired signals on Island piles have not been disturbed by the noise caused by the free shaft in the water.

IMPLEMENTATION OF PIT TESTS RESULTS IN THE DESIGN

The report of PIT results was accepted by the client after only one round of comments and allowed for the confirmation/determination of all the data required for the structural verification of the piles in view of their reuse to support the new loads applied for BMP Project, and hence to design accordingly the strengthening and modification works of the above water structures.

A grid of underwater bracings was also designed to interconnect the piles and hence to reduce their slenderness in view of the current Eurocode limits. New anodes (18no.s) and new Transformer/Rectifiers (2no.s) have been added to protect this new bracing grid.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The information gathered thanks to the PIT campaign has been essential to integrate the data available from existing drawings, visual surveys and geotechnical investigation and hence to allow for confirming the sustainable decision to reuse existing piles for the new marine loading facilities.

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